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HUMAN CONNECTIONS PROJECT: EXPANDING WORLDVIEWS

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ABSTRACT

The "Human Connections: Expanding Worldview" Project, coordinated by the author and psychoanalyst Renata Evangelista through the Association of Teaching Professionals of the Municipality of Mauá (APROMAM), aimed to promote self-knowledge, encourage reading, critical thinking, and understanding of others. Designed for associated educators from municipal schools in Mauá/SP-Brazil, the project consisted of monthly online meetings focused on sharing books. Participants' written work was submitted via email under pseudonyms to protect their anonymity, as it addressed personal aspects, connecting literary content to their experiences. The project thus sought to encourage personal growth and the exchange of opinions, promoting a greater connection between project members and the world around them.

Keywords: Self-awareness. Teacher training. Reading and critical thinking. Human connections.